

THE FEATURES OF TRANSLATION AND ITS HISTORY

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the topic of theory and tasks of translation. The article discusses the problems that researchers may encounter in the process of translation.*

Keywords: *translation studies, activity, theory, task, goal, scientific analysis, linguistics, translation problems, communication.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА И ЕГО ИСТОРИЯ

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена теме теории и задач перевода. В статье рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми исследователи могут столкнуться в процессе перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *переводоведение, деятельность, теория, задача, цель, научный анализ, языкознание, проблемы перевода, коммуникация.*

Among the numerous complex problems that modern linguistics studies, an important place is occupied by the study of the linguistic aspects of interlingual speech activity, which is called “translation” or “translation activity”.

Translation is a complex multifaceted phenomenon, some aspects of which can be the subject of research by various sciences. Within the framework of translation studies, psychological, literary, ethnographic and other aspects of translation activity are studied, as well as the history of translation activity in a particular country or countries. Depending on the subject of research, one can single out psychological translation studies (translation psychology), literary translation studies (the theory of artistic or literary translation), ethnographic translation studies, historical translation studies, etc. The leading place in modern translation studies belongs to linguistic translation studies (linguistics of translation), which studies translation as linguistic phenomenon. Separate types of translation studies complement each other, striving for a comprehensive description of translation activities.

The purpose of translation is to acquaint the reader as closely as possible with a text in a foreign language that he does not know.

To translate means to express correctly and completely by means of one language what has already been expressed earlier by means of another language.” Translation can be carried out, firstly, from one language to another unrelated, related, closely related, secondly, from a literary language to a dialect and vice versa, thirdly, from the language of the ancient period to the modern language.

The history of translation can be focused on the practice of translation and on the theory of translation. In the first case, the researcher is interested in: what is translated, by whom it is translated, in what conditions translation activities are carried out, in what social and political context. The history of translation involves a description of how the translator himself perceives his work, how translation evolved in different eras and in different cultures, what recommendations translators gave to their colleagues and how they taught translation, how translation discourse correlated with other discursive practices of the era. Foundational English-language works on the history of translation in the 20th century: Theodore Savory “The Art of

Translation” (1957), George Steiner “After Babel” (1975), Luis Kelly “The True Interpreter” (1979), Susan Bassnett “Translation Studies” (1980).

A separate problem of the history of translation: the analysis of translation models that arose as the theory and practice of translation activities improved.

Subsequently what are the tasks of translation theory? This question was partially answered by the English researcher T. Savory. He brought together the main requirements for translation by various authors, and came up with an interesting list, where mutually exclusive principles are placed side by side:

- *the translation must convey the words of the original; the translation must convey the thoughts of the original; the translation must be read like the original;*
- *the translation should read like a translation;*
- *the translation should reflect the style of the original;*
- *the translation should reflect the style of the translator;*
- *the translation should be read as a work contemporary with the original;*
- *the translation should be read as a work contemporary to the translator;*
- *the translation may allow additions and omissions; the translation should not allow additions and omissions; translation of poetry should be carried out in prose; translation of poems should be carried out in poetic form.*

The theory of translation in its linguistic aspect analyzes, explains and generalizes the facts of translation experience, establishes correspondences and discrepancies between languages. Based on the general patterns identified by the theory of translation, specific conclusions can be drawn in the future in relation to particular cases.

Translation theory is, actually, a descriptive theoretical discipline that deals with the identification and description of the objective laws of the translation process, which are based on the structural features and rules of functioning of the languages involved in this process. In other words, the theory of translation describes not what should be, but what is, what constitutes the nature of the phenomenon under study. At the same time, based on the description of the linguistic mechanism of translation, it is possible to formulate some normative recommendations, principles and rules, methods and techniques of translation, following which the translator can more successfully solve the tasks facing him. In all cases, scientific analysis of observed facts precedes normative prescriptions.

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